

Deliverable 2.1

Online training material: 1st and 2nd workshop

Version 1

WP 2
Deliverable 2.1
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Executive summary

This document outlines the successful transition of learning materials from the first two GRINNAQUA workshops to our website, where they are now publicly available. This includes any materials the lecturers agreed to make publicly available. Unfortunately, this did not include all the presentations from the workshops as some included sensitive information that the lecturers volunteered to present but were either not comfortable with making them available or not allowed due to IPR issues.

This strategic move aligns with GRINNAQUA's commitment to provide highly specialized training and promote continuous learning, enhancing accessibility, and expanding the reach of educational initiatives. The initiative not only facilitated the ongoing professional development but also opened up opportunities for a broader audience to benefit from the knowledge and insights shared during the workshops. This effort is set to maximize the project's impact and foster a culture of ongoing skill development in a more accessible and flexible manner.

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1. Introduction

Work Package 2 was designed to deliver targeted training sessions on a broad range of aquatic animal health topics, encompassing not only theoretical lectures and seminars but also hands-on analytical procedures and *in silico* analytical tools. The objectives were to: i) enhance the knowledge and technical capabilities of the Widening institution, external researchers and students; ii) facilitate communication between the scientific community and national industry stakeholders, fostering an exchange of challenges and solutions; and iii) promote short-term international exchanges among researchers, facilitating knowledge transfer and establishing long-term collaborations.

Aligned with GRINNAQUA's commitment to provide highly specialized training and promote continuous learning, a new page was added to our website for easier access to the resources produced during the project. These include communication materials for the project, which may be useful for those interested in quickly learning more about the project, as well as the learning materials from the workshops. This later content is only made available with a clear authorization from the authors.

Furthermore, a YouTube channel was created where materials from the project will be continuously uploaded, including workshop lesson recordings.

<https://www.youtube.com/@GRINNAQUAEU>

2. Workshop 1: increasing researcher's skills on the use of omics tools

Cutting-edge technologies, like -omics tools, are progressively used to generate vast datasets, offering a comprehensive view of organism responses to external stimuli. Notably, the exploration of immune responses and disease resistance stands to gain significantly from these

analytical approaches. Workshop 1 was spearheaded by UEDIN, with a wealth of expertise in both laboratory and *in silico* applications of these techniques. The incorporation of these analytical competences will substantially enhance CIIMAR's work.

The workshop took place in Leça da Palmeira, on the 16 and 17th of March 2023 and was mostly attended by researchers. Due to space limitations, 40 participants were selected based on the relevance of the workshop content to their current research.

2.1. Learning materials

Unfortunately, due to a technical issue it was not possible to record the lesson and the partners from UEDIN are now recording the lesson again so it can be made available on YouTube. All support learning materials were made available during the workshop by giving the participants access to a repository with presentations and practical examples. Due to the nature of this course, all of its content is publicly available on GitHub. Links to all learning materials were added to the project website. The videos will be upload to our YouTube channel before the end of month 17 and links will be added to the website.

[grinnaqua.eu | training](http://grinnaqua.eu/training)

3. Workshop 2: Fish vaccination

The second workshop focused on vaccination as a growing and so far best prophylactic strategy to safeguard fish health in the aquaculture industry. Research efforts are directed towards innovating technologies like DNA and RNA fish vaccines, anticipated for easier administration and heightened efficacy. The workshop's primary speakers were predominantly researchers from the Fish Immunology and Pathology group of CSIC, who were the main organizers of the workshop. They also invited leading experts from both research and industry for a more diverse and wider approach to the topic.

The workshop took place in Porto, on the 18 and 19th of October 2023. This workshop was on high demand and counted with participation from both the research and the industry community, including farmers as well as feed and vaccine producers. Due to space limitations for practical classes, which were held in ICBAS, allowing to accommodate a bigger group, 40 participants were selected based on the relevance of the workshop content to their current research. Because of the high demand we further selected 10 more participants to attend the theoretical session.

3.1. Learning materials

Before the course all teachers were asked permission to record their lessons. Unfortunately, because some of them were from the industry, they were not able to provide clearance to use this resource due to IPR issues and could not provide the presentations afterwards. Presentation from the remaining ones were recorded and edited to remove any content they did not wish to disclose to the larger public. Edited presentation, removing such information, were provided by the teacher after the course and the resources were made available to the students by email. The learning resources were afterwards uploaded to our website. The recordings will be uploaded to YouTube at a later stage, once we are able to upload contents from the 1st workshop, so we can make them available in chronological order.

[grinnaqua.eu | training](https://grinnaqua.eu/training)

4. Intellectual property course: protection and valorisation

GRINNAQUA joined efforts with BlueBio4Future, another Horizon Europe proposal coordinated by the widening institution, to offer a course on the protection and valorisation of intellectual property with practical examples from the aquaculture sector. We were able to count with the expertise from a company dedicated to IP protection, Patentree, and with the experience from other institutions that were open to share their know-how with CIIMAR. This included INIA-CSIC, a partner in GRINNAQUA. It also counted with a round table where different perspectives were shared and an opportunity for the participants to ask more specific questions was possible.

The demand for this course was much higher than our expectations, forcing us to close registrations earlier as logistics did not allow for a larger group.

Unfortunately, due to the nature of the course and because the content was prepared by a company, we were not able to share any resources from the course.

More information about the course can be found on the project website:

[grinnaqua.eu | training](http://grinnaqua.eu/training)

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